

CAUSES OF LOW ACHIEVEMENT OF UNIVERSITY' STUDENTS FROM THEIR POINTS OF VIEW

Kahtan Ahmed Al-Dahir

Professor in the Al-Ahliyya Amman University

ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to investigate the causes of low achievement from student's points of view for both sexes by various levels and faculties.(106) students took place in the at Al-Ahliyya Amman University (AAU).

A questionnaire was formed and applied, after its validity and reliability were verified. The study resulted in following points :-

The weight of low achievement causes are moderate in four dimensions (Faculty member , students , methods of assessment, course content)while the weight of family factors dimension was high. There are no significant differences at the level of $\alpha \leq 0.05$ in low achievement causes according to gender, the level of study and according to the faculty specialization in three dimensions (Faculty member , methods of assessment, Course content)while there are significant differences at the level of $\alpha \leq 0.05$ in two dimensions (students and family factors)in behalf of engineering faculty) .

KEYWORDS

Faculty member , students , methods of assessment, course content ,Family

1. INTRODUCTION

The universities are the backbone of the state, which provides the country with all the competencies, and take the initiative in building and improvement the country to what it aspires to. However, countries may differ in how to pay attention to this development according to many variables economic, social, cultural, political and educational, and these variables are still changing, the outlook is not the same in different countries. However, Education is a priority for States because it is the cornerstone of building any nation. But a number of students may suffer from many problems related to various aspects as family problems, the relation with teachers, methods of evaluation and curricula. In this sense, some students may fail to reach the success rate, which is one of the most important problems facing the universities. It is not easy to determine the reasons for this. There are many factors, including students, social, economic and cultural conditions, local environment, emotional stability and social adjustment and recent developments that may negatively affect the student's achievement, especially the Internet and mobile phone, and many parents and teachers complain of this phenomenon, which has become rampant. We all know that the Internet and mobile phone take a very long time, which adversely affect the requirements of academic aspects. Thus, the delay of graduation will increase the burden of families, and will delay in participating in the service of the community in which they live, and this is wasteful the time and money . The reasons are not limited to students and family circumstances, but there are many other reasons related to teacher and his cognitive, social, professional and personal characteristics, the assessment methods used, and the content of the course has an impact.

1.1. Research Problem

The problem of low achievement of students is one of the most important problems facing educational institutions, which may negatively affect student's behavior as they may be relieved of academic delay to undesirable conduct, and one of the most popular theories that explain aggressive behavior is frustration induced aggression (Al-Dahir, 2015) .As well as its negative impact on the economic, psychological , educational aspects and its affect on the relationship between teachers and students as the teacher is often comfortable with the efficient student who meets the requirements of the university. In addition has negative impact on academic self concept.

Therefore, this study aimed at identifying the reasons leading to the low academic achievement of students, and are there statistically significant differences according to gender ,study stage, specialization variables.

1.2. Study Questions

1. What are the reasons for the low academic achievement of students ?
2. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05 α) of the reasons leading to the low academic achievement of the university students according to gender , study stage , specialization(faculty) variables.

1.3. The Importance of The Study

1. It is an attempt to shed light on the phenomenon prevalent in university education which is low academic achievement of university students .
2. It stands on the reasons that lead to the decline of university students academically and therefore can be developed strategies that alleviate these problems and access to students to the acceptable level that benefits the students , families, teachers and the whole community.
3. The study may contribute to providing feedback to the university administration and faculties .
4. The results of this study can serve as a theoretical framework for researchers interested in youth problems in general and university education in particular.

1.4. Previous Studies

Many studies have been conducted in this field , Talafha (2006) found that the lack of pre-preparation of the subjects is the most important personal reasons, and the methods of university teaching, which focus on memorization were the most important educational reasons, while parent authoritarian style was the most important social reasons affected the low cumulative rates of students who have warning. The results also indicated that there is no statistically significant differences between males and females for the most important personal, educational and social reasons.

While Mkumbo & Amani (2012) found that the reasons of failure and success are due to internal factors are the internal locus of control and emotional stability and self-control.

Al-Huli and Sheldan (2012) reached that economic reasons is the most negative reasons that affected the continuation of students for their higher studies followed by social reasons and then educational reasons and personal reasons.

-Najimi, Sharifirad, Amini(2013)found the most important reasons leading to failure of students were the curriculums(0.65 ± 4), the factors related to the educators (0.55 ± 3.88), the learning environment (0.62 ± 3.63), the family factors (3.53 ± 3.6) and socioeconomic factors (0.69 ± 3.45).

Muhasna and his colleagues (2013) study showed that the educational reasons are more influential in the low cumulative rates of students followed by social and economic reasons, The personal reasons were the last one.

In this context Tachie &Chiresha(2013)reached in their study to external factors such as lack of human and material resources, poor teachers, poor teaching methods and some learners attributed their failure to internal factors like laziness, lack of interest and absenteeism While study of Reda&Mulugeta(2018)reached to student interest, study habit and previous background factors have a significant effect on the academic performance of students. Lastly Tabassum Khan &Ahmed (2018) revealed in their study the negative impact of facebook addiction on academic achievement .

The previous studies show that there is some similarity between the variables dealt with and the current study. However, the current study was characterized as more comprehensive, as it was dealt with five main dimensions which included the faculty member , student , methods of assessment , course content and family.

The researcher believes that these five variables are the main ones affecting the low academic achievement of students, while most of the previous studies have covered the dimensions of three such as Talafaha (2006), Mkumbo & Amani, (2013) , Tachie &Chiresha(2013). The current study did not rely only on previous studies and the broad personal experience of the researcher but also asked an open question to a sample of 120 students about the reasons that lead to low achievement.

2. STUDY POPULATION

The study population was consisted of (106) students from three basic faculties which represent the largest number and the largest number of low achievers, namely the Faculty of Pharmacy and Medical Sciences and the Faculty of Engineering, including the Department of Architecture and the Faculty of Administrative and Financial Sciences at (AAU).This is what the researcher have collected through the official statistics obtained by the Admissions and Registration Department.

2.1 Study instrument

The research required to develop a questionnaire covering all the possible variables that lead to the low academic achievement of students based on previous studies and personal experience in the field of teaching for more than (35) years of the various stages, in addition, an open question to (120) male and female asking them (what are the causes which lead to Low academic achievement ?

2.1.1. Validity

The initial questionnaire which consisted of (88) paragraphs were presented to a group of arbitrators, most of them hold the professorship with PhD from faculties of educational sciences at Amman University, the Arab University of Amman

The paragraphs remained which agreed more than 90% by the arbitrators and became 70 paragraphs for five dimensions .

2.1.2 Reliability

The reliability of the instrument has been verified by calculating the internal consistency coefficients in the half-split and alpha-Cronbach methods. The following table illustrates that

Table (1) illustrates reliability

Dimensions	Alpha-Cronbach	Half-split
Faculty member	0.761	0.789
Students	0.865	0.778
Evaluation methods	0.855	0.732
Course content	0.666	0.715
The family	0.817	0.792
total	0.916	0.832

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 With Regard To The Question: What Are The Reasons That Lead To Low Academic Achievement?

Table (2) The means and standard deviations of the five variables are arranged in descending order.

Dimension	Number	Means	Standard deviation	Weight
Reasons related to Family	106	3.6996	1.23978	High
Reasons related to Faculty member	106	3.1570	.90194	moderate
Reasons related to students	106	3.1370	084962	moderate
Reasons related to content	106	2.9582	.95444	moderate
Reasons related to assessment style	106	2.8498	.777369	moderate
Total (Five dimensions)	106	.68092	3.1632	moderate

The above table shows that the family dimension is the most important reasons for the low academic achievement, where the weight of this dimension was high while the weight of the other dimensions were moderate with varying degrees. The following table clarifies the paragraphs on this dimension and will be commented on each of these dimensions:

Table(3) Means and Standard deviations for reasons related to the faculty member arranged in descending order.

Number	Paragraph	Number	Means	Standard deviation	Weight
1	The faculty member makes fun of the students.	106	4.04362	1.23978	High
2	Lack of scientific and practical experience.	106	3.5189	1.30370	moderate
3	His voice is monotonous and does not raise or lower his voice as required.	106	3.2736	1.23853	moderate
4	The participation of students in demonstrating their creative potential is not sufficiently open.	106	3.2642	1.31874	moderate
5	Faculty member is not open with students.	106	3.2358	1.10023	moderate
6	Does not vary in teaching methods and techniques .	106	3.2358	2.02859	moderate
6	The lack of a clear plan for the Faculty member makes students do not know what they read.	106	3.2358	1.28398	moderate
7	The Faculty member style is not fair in his dealings with students.	106	3.2075	1.37125	moderate
8	He does not show enthusiasm in his lecture.	106	3.1321	1.10476	moderate
9	He does not give students enough attention to academic counseling.	106	3.0566	1.32255	moderate
10	We do not feel the roles of faculty member which should assume, like the father, the guide or the counselor.	106	3.0000	1.30931	moderate
11	Do not use reinforcement and encouragement.	106	2.9528	1.38964	moderate
12	Focuses on the negative aspects of students more than the positives.	106	2.9434	1.32255	moderate
13	Do not use modern teaching techniques in teaching adequately and appropriately .	106	2.9340	1.34709	mode
14	Teaching almost concentrates on the theoretical aspect without giving attention to the practical and applied aspects.	106	2.9245	1.34305	moderate
15	The weakness of linking the lecture material with real life experiences .	106	2.8679	1.34572	moderate
16	The method of simplification is not used in the presentation of the course material.	106	2.6887	1.26764	moderate

It is clear from the table that these reasons are real reasons that affect students' achievement. The weight of all paragraphs are moderate except one with high weight which is (the faculty member make fun of the students), it was given higher importance as a reason for low achievement. It can

be said that there is a dynamic relation between the teacher and the course , if the student loves the teacher he will mostly love the course and vice versa. He must also be fair in his dealing with students.

The researcher constantly emphasizes to make the learner in a good psychological position by keeping him away from any cases of failure or frustration. The paragraph (lack of scientific and knowledge expertise) in second place, it should be said that teaching is both science and art , and science alone is not enough to make the learner active , but there is a need for using techniques in how to display the material in an interesting way to draw self-attention, and to show enthusiasm in his lecture to increase their motivation which is leading to effective interaction between the faculty member and students and among students themselves that will open the way for exploiting their potential . The faculty member must use reinforcement of various types and feedback . He is supposed to focus on the positive aspects of the student which is regarded the best way to overcome negative aspects . This strategy is not limited to educational institutions only, but can be used in many places such as family, work, various departments and others. He must also diversify the teaching methods to keep the student away from boredom and keep or raise motivation, and to connect material to life, and he must give attention to the practical and applied aspects that will lead to the students satisfaction.

The faculty member is supposed to control his voice and not be at one tone, but to raise his voice or reduce it according to the importance of the points it raises. Lastly, the faculty member is supposed to facilitate the course material by linking them as much as possible with realistic examples.

Therefore, Non-compliance of the previous points may limit the motivation of students in the effort and perseverance, which leads to low academic achievement. The present study has in some respects been matched by Talafha (2006); Najimi, Sharifirad, Amini and Meftagh(2009); Al-Huli and Chaldean (2012), and Mohsena, et al. (2013).

It is clear that the student is the most important factor leading to the low academic achievement . The weight of all the paragraphs were moderate except one was high weight (lack of self-confidence) which affects negatively on the exploitation of self-actual potential, as well as affect on student motivation.

The five paragraphs (2,3,4,5)are very important reasons affecting low achievement . The use of psychotropic substances is a real reason for the low achievement of students and this is in line with logic and many studies have proven this, for example, the study (Balsa, Giuliano and French, 2011). The student may stumbled if he is not interested in specialization, since specialization may not be his real choice, but in accordance with the parents' wishes, or his average degree enforced him to specialize, or his financial inability enforced him to choose the specialization, or he may not have a background about specialization.

A paragraph (4) Students may feel frustrated by traditional teaching with limited thinking, without opportunities to ignite internal strengths and potentials, and creative thinking opportunities. The fifth paragraph indicate that university differs from the schools because it includes students from different environments within the country as well as quite a few countries, some of which find it difficult to adapt and meet the requirements of the study. Some may not have enough ambition (mention in 6 paragraph) for effort and perseverance, especially those who live in luxury and wealth. There is a link between ambition and motivation and, if the ambition is weak or absent then motivation is weak or absent (Makamure,2018) . Additionally, motivation is very important factor affecting achievement. Many studies have indicated that like, Dickson,2018.

Table(4) Means and Standard deviations for reasons related to students arranged in descending order

Number	Paragraph	Number	Means	Standard deviation	Weight
1	Lack of self-confidence.	106	3.7170	1.32201	High
2	Substance abuse.	106	3.5189	1.40225	moderate
3	Not interested in specialization	106	3.5189	1.40903	moderate
4	Lack of opportunities for students to use their creative abilities during the study.	106	3.4811	1.38173	moderate
5	Can not compete with peers who came from different educational institutions	106	3.4245	2.88391	moderate
6	Weakness of ambition.	106	3.4245	1/45372	moderate
7	Frequent absence of lectures attendance	106	3.3491	1.30232	moderate
8	Not adaptive to peers.	106	3.3302	3.29999	moderate
9	Fun and entertainment are preferred during the lecture	106	3.3019	1.41536	moderate
10	Not emotionally stable	106	3.2264	1.41612	moderate
11	Having bad friends.	106	3.1792	1.59043	moderate
12	He does not like studying	106	3.1321	1.30986	moderate
13	Feel ashamed especially with the opposite sex.	106	3.00660	1.48175	moderate
14	Lack of motivation	106	3.0566	1.39270	moderate
15	Stay up late at night to watch movies	106	3.0556	1.36508	moderate
16	Insufficient health.	106	2.9810	1.32999	moderate
17	The use of mobile phone and other programs distracted from the lecture.	106	2.9623	1.49873	moderate
18	Depending on electronic registration without benefiting from academic counseling.	106	2.8774	1.40545	moderate
19	Lack of sleep for pathological anxiety.	106	2.8208	1.39248	moderate
20	Weakness of the student's ability to remember the information he studied during the exam.	106	2.7453	1.33139	moderate
21	Engage in emotional and sexual thinking.	106	2.6887	1.31919	moderate
22	Mentally displaced during the lecture.	106	2.6792	1.19958	moderate
23	Unable to study systematically.	106	2.6415	1.19673	moderate

The frequent absence of lectures attendance \ is a real reason for the decline of academic achievement, this may be due to the luxury and well-being which he lives or his circumstances enforced him to work to meet his needs and family ,or he may responsible of patient in his home, and this is what the researcher touched during his teaching. Also, when a student is not adaptive with his peers or has poor compatibility, whatever their causes will appear to be negative in their achievement. Many studies pointed out the adaptive skills and achievement for example Raines and his colleagues ,2017.

Some students are not serious to learn ,they prefer fun and entertainment in the lecture Which affect their achievement . Maladjustment is a real reason for low achievement . It affects developmental aspects such as attention ,perception. Thinking. Maladjustment can be linked with paragraph Weakness of the student's ability to remember the information he studied during the exam. Bad friends also have a negative impact on their achievement. They are often drifted into unacceptable socially actions that may be waste of time and may sometimes lead to psychotropic substances. A bad friend can pull a student to do illegal acts. The lack of motivation(as mentioned before) is a real reason for the low achievement of students.

Health inefficiency may be associated with motivation as it negatively affects active participation and effort because the bad health aspect may be Impedes his self-potentials . Another reason , many low-achievers watch for long hours films and videos , especially bad ones, which affects their commitment to permanence, and affect their attention to the lecture because the student does not have enough sleep and be exhausted during the day, lack of sleeping can also cause inability to concentrate, yawning, moodiness, fatigue ,irritability, depressed mood ,difficulty learning new concepts, forgetfulness ,lack of motivation. The lack of sleep may be the result of anxiety, the most serious of which is a negative effect on follow-up and attention. It may hinder the retrieval of information from memory, and we advise students to stay away from excessive anxiety because it inhibits recalling . The preoccupation with emotional and sexual thinking and dissociation of the mind during the lecture, especially negatively affects the materials that need attention and a strong focus toward the teacher such as mathematics, statistics, physics and chemistry. A paragraph that was unable to study in a systematic manner had the least impact on academic achievement. It should be noted that the paragraphs do not have the same affect on achievement. In the same time, there is a link among paragraphs for example (2,7,8,9,10,11,13, 14,15,19).

Table(5) Means and Standard deviations for reasons related to assessment methods arranged in descending order

Number	Paragraph	Number	Means	Standard deviation	Weight
1	Questions are limited to the objective type without Editorial	106	3.3208	1.19952	moderate
2	The examination questions are not at the heart of the subject.	106	3.2453	1.27848	moderate
3	The distribution of marks to questions is not objective.	106	3.0660	1.20530	moderate
4	Questions do not cover all the course.	106	3.0377	1.21047	moderate
5	The evaluation process does not pay attention to the creative aspect.	106	2.9623	1.25679	moderate
6	Tests are based primarily on mute remembering .	106	2.9151	1.20410	moderate
7	The tests are not clear.	106	2.9057	1.30587	moderate
8	The examinations do not take into account individual differences.	106	2.8208	1.20946	moderate
9	Exams difficulty.	106	2.6132	1.31345	moderate
10	Assessment is based primarily on tests.	106	2.4717	1.32527	moderate

Assessment methods may have an impact on academic achievement but do not reach the level of other dimensions as shown in Table (3) The Paragraph "Questions are limited to the objective type without editorial " depends primarily on the memorization without the questions that open the door to the student to achieve himself through the presentation of self-opinions and the use of creative thinking, and this paragraph is linked to a paragraph "the evaluation process does not pay attention to the creative aspect ", Very important because it is a step that open the way for creative ideas that serve the community rather than memorization Therefore, the researcher believes that the teaching methods that universities follow in general and the means of evaluation need to be re-considered so as to make the student active through non-formal teaching and self-reliance because the best types of learning is self-learning, which leads to the state of creativity and innovation. It is also supposed to take into consideration the creative flame and bright glimpses and assessment is not limited to tests only such as peer and self-assessment in collaborative learning activities.

The evaluation process should take into account individual differences, be clear and precise and do not go beyond the subject. However ,assessment is a vital component of effective teaching practice as teachers and learners cannot avoid giving and getting feedback from any learning activity. Learning assessment is concerned with practices that maximize the value of the feedback process to ensure that learning is optimized. Feedback ranges from the informal(e.g. oral comments given immediately to learners as they think through problems), to more formal(e.g. written feedback ,(Cambridge Assessment International Education).

Table(7) Means and Standard deviations for reasons related to family arranged in descending order

Number	Paragraph	Number	Means	Standard deviation	Weight
1	Disintegration of the family	106	4.0377	2.05950	High
2	His relationship with family is not good	106	3.9717	1.36247	High
3	The quarrels and the constant fight between the parents	106	3.8491	1.34372	High
4	The family does not support the student financially and morally.	106	3.7925	1.41903	High
5	Divorce parents.	106	3.7264	1.57681	High
6	Parents compulsory treatment.	106	3.6226	1.47650	moderate
7	parents Separation.	106	3.6132	1.55882	moderate
8	Poor parents' interest in the future of their children.	106	3.5943	1.57830	moderate
9	The student does not feel the family's interest.	106	3.5943	1.52926	moderate
10	Parental disease .	106	3.4623	1.52549	moderate
11	The family suffers from economic problems.	106	3.4340	1.53076	moderate
12	Family is not educated .	106	3.10236	1.35464	moderate

It is clear from the table that the reasons related to family have taken a higher weight than the other dimensions, which proves that these reasons have a significant impact on academic achievement because the student needs peace of mind and stability so that his mind focuses on learning and achievement and active participation in classroom activities.

The warm and intimate relationship between the parents reflects positively on the relationship with their young adults and the relationship of the adults among them. Therefore, improper family

conditions such as family disintegration, divorce or separation of parents, parental illness or poor relationship between the student and his family and lack of interest in it or the family's economic suffering all have an impact on achievement . There are many studies that have shown the influence of family factors on achievement such as Hill & Tyson (2009)who analyzed 50 studies in this regard and showing the close relationship between family factors and achievement. Many other studies have shown the relationship between family factors and achievement,like,Mathoni,2013;Doly ,2018. The results of this study have in some respects been consistent with Najimi, Sharifirad, Amini and Meftagh(2009); Trchie& hiresha(2013).

3.2. With Regard To: Are There Differences According To Gender Variable

Table (8) Differences between students according to gender variable

Dimension	Category	Number	Means	Standard deviation	df	T value	Sig
Faculty member	Males	77	3.0794	.86746	104	1.45	.607
	Females	29	3.3631	.97346			
Students	Males	77	3.1423	.84489	104	.104	.626
	Females	29	3.1229	.87699			
Assessment methods	Males	77	2.7511	.74847	104	2.179	.306
	Females	29	3.1121	.80650			
Course content	Males	77	2.8757	.96177	104	1.472	.937
	Females	29	3.1773	.87952			
Family	Males	77	3.6907	1.26108	104	.123	.900
	Females	29	3.7241	1.20273			
Total	Males	77	3.1185	.64334	104	1.078	.183
	Females	29	3.2793	.77205			

There were no statistically significant differences according to the gender variable in all dimensions. This indicates the convergence of views, especially since women played a large role in society in light of globalization, which had a great role in raising women's awareness of their rights. They participated in most areas of life, as well as university life does not differentiate between the males and females, each of them have rights and duties do not differ. Therefore, the view of the previous variables was converged. The results of the present study were consistent with the results of the study of Huli and Shaldan (2012)., Yagan wali, Ali and Bufarafa, (2015) and Talafaha (2006), while there were differences according to the gender variable in the educational dimension in the study of Muhasna and his colleagues (2013).

3.3 With Regard To : Are There Differences According To The Variable Of The Study Stage.

Table (9) The mean and standard deviations according to study stage variable

dimension	the study stage	Number	Means	Standard deviation
Faculty member	Second	23	3.1662	1,09571
	Third	32	3.2224	.99991
	forth	51	3.1119	.74520
	total	106	3.1570	.90194
Students	Second	23	2.9887	.89683
	Third	32	3.2595	.68260
	fourth	51	3.1270	.92374
	total	106	3.1370	.84962
Assessment methods	Second	23	2.8225	.78347
	Third	32	2.9271	.82841
	fourth	51	2.8137	.74565
	total	106	2.8498	.77369
Course content	Second	23	2.6087	.90168
	Third	32	3.1830	.84573
	fourth	51	2.9748	.99374
	total	106	2.9582	.94555
Family	Second	23	3.4229	1.42411
	Third	32	3.9858	.86252
	forth	51	3.6453	1.38388
	total	106	3.6998	1.23978
Total	Second	23	3.0335	.70849
	Third	32	3.3000	.60543
	fourth	51	3.1359	.71068
	total	106	3.1832	.68092

The table above shows that the means in the first dimension are almost convergent, but the means in the family dimension is higher than the other dimensions. The total score (3.6996) is of high weight and the lowest is related to course content (2.9582) The statistical significance can be determined by analyzing the co-variance .

Table (10) one way -variance analysis of the variables of the study stage

Variables	Source	Some of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig
Faculty member	Between groups	.243	2	.121	.147	.864
	Within groups	85.174	103	.827		
	Total	85.417	105			
Students	Between groups	.991	2	.496	.683	.508
	Within groups	74.804	103	.726		
	Total	75795	105			
Assessment methods	Between groups	.275	2	.137	.226	.798
	Within groups	62.578	103	.608		
	Total	62.853	105			
Course content	Between groups	4.441	2	2.221	2.557	.082
	Within groups	89.435	103	.868		
	Total	93.876	105			
Family	Between groups	4.532	2	2.268	1.488	.231
	Within groups	156.859	103	1.523		
	Total	161.391	105			
Total	Between groups	1.024	2	.512	1.106	.335
	Within groups	47.659	103	.463		
	Total	48.683	105			

The results show that there are no statistically significant differences on all dimensions, which, the perception of the reasons for the low academic achievement was close to the three stages (second, third and fourth), especially in the Semester system which is different from annual system ,as it may three stages available in the same course in the Semester system.

3.4 With Regard To : Are There Differences According To The Specialization Variable .

Table (11) means and standard deviations according to the specialization variable

Dimension	Specialization(faculty)	Number	Means	Standard deviation
Faculty member	Pharmacy	41	3.3286	1,06396
	Engineering	35	3.0739	.68960
	Admin& Financial Sciences	30	3.0196	.87007
	Total	106	3.1570	.90194
Students	Pharmacy	41	3.0979	.84887
	Engineering	35	3.4484	.81809
	Administrative & Financial Sciences	30	2.8275	.78531
	Total	106	3.1370	.08252
Assessment methods	Pharmacy	41	2.8516	.12057
	Engineering	35	2.9595	.11353
	Administrative Financial Sciences	30	2.7198	.16168
	Total	106	2.8498	.07515
Course content	Pharmacy	41	2.9756	.12825
	Engineering	35	3.0490	.13533
	Administrative & Financial Sciences	30	2.8286	.22566
	Total	106	2.9582	.09184
Family	Pharmacy	41	3.5477	.19176
	Engineering	35	4.1584	.19524
	Administrative & Financial Sciences	30	3.3727	.22541
	Total	106	3.6998	.12042
Total	Pharmacy	41	3.1700	.11242
	Engineering	35	3.3453	.09289
	Administrative & Financial Sciences	30	2.9414	.13152
	Total	106	3.1632	.06614

It is clear from the table in general that the results were close except in the dimensions of students and the family. The mean of the Faculty of Engineering (3.4484) was higher than the means of the Faculty of Pharmacy and Medical Sciences (3.0979) and the Faculty of Administrative and Financial Sciences (2.8275).the same in regard to family ,the mean of Engineering faculty was (4.1584) while the Faculty of Pharmacy and Medical Sciences (3.5477) and the Faculty of Administrative and Financial Sciences (3.3727). The following is a one way -variance analysis test to determine the significance of differences.

Table (12) one way -variance analysis indicate the differences in the response of students according to the variable of specialization (Faculty).

Variables	Source	Some of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig
Faculty member	Between groups	2.014	2	1.007	1.244	.293
	Within groups	83.402	103	.810		
	Total	85.417	105			
Students	Between groups	6.332	2	3.166	4.694	.011
	Within groups	69.463	103	.674		
	Total	75.795	105			
Assessment methods	Between groups	.931	2	.446	.775	.464
	Within groups	61.922	103	.601		
	Total	62.853	105			
Course content	Between groups	.805	2	.402	.445	.082
	Within groups	93.071	103	.904		
	Total	93.876	105			
Family	Between groups	11.520	2	5.760	3.959	.022
	Within groups	149.871	103	1.445		
	Total	161.391	105			
Total	Between groups	2.638	2	1.319	2.951	.057
	Within groups	46.045	103	.447		
	Total	48.683	105			

The table shows that there were no statistically significant differences in the three dimensions (faculty member, evaluation methods and course content), while significant differences were observed at (0.05 α) in the students and family dimensions. The family, in all its variants, is the basis for the formation of the basic features of the personality, which greatly affect the academic self concept. It is the first environment for emotional and social learning, so it affects the educational achievement more than the other variables .

To find out the significance of the variance of any faculty ,scheffe test was used

Table (13) Scheffe test to determine the significance differences

Dimension	Faculties	Means differences	Sig	Low value	Upper value
Students	Engineering Pharmacy Administrative & Financial Sciences	.35089 .27002	.184 .395	.8203 .2200	.1185 .7601
	Pharmacy Engineering Administrative and Financial	.35089 .62091	.184 .012	.1185 .1134	.8203 1.1284
	Pharmacy Administrative & Financial Engineering	.27002 .62091	.395 .012	.7601 1.1284	.2200 .1134
Family	Engineering Pharmacy Administrative and Financial Sciences	.61077 .17494	.094 .834	1.3003 .5449	.0787 .8984
	Pharmacy Engineering Administrative & Financial	.61077 .78571	.094 .036	.0787 .0403	1.3003 1.5312
	Pharmacy Administrative & Financial Engineering	.17494 .78571	.843 .036	.8948 1.5312	.5449 .0403

The table shows that the differences between the three faculties are in favor of the Faculty of Engineering in both the students and the family dimensions, where the significance was in dimension of the students (.012) and in the dimension of the family (.036). This means that the students of the Faculty of Engineering responded to reasons related to students' as actual reasons leading to low academic achievement. It may be said that creative thinking is more clear in the Faculty of Engineering, and this requires creating a positive atmosphere conducive to creative thinking so the reasons related to the student and family may affect them more than others.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Diversity in evaluation methods to take into account individual differences and creative aspects of students.
2. The focus of the faculty member on the positive aspects of students and keep them away from any kind of failure and frustration and ridicule.
3. The faculty member supposed to play his role as a leader, counselor and educator by opening the door wide to students to vent their various problems because the faculty member represents alternative father in the university
4. Use different educational methods and techniques and modern educational Technologies.
5. Linking the material to practical life as much as possible.
6. Counseling students is very necessary according to the guidance plan.
7. Urge students to take care of their health and take adequate sleep to be ready to prepare for comprehending the lectures.
8. Provide students with additional references other than the book test to benefit more and remove what is unclear .
9. Mass media must take it role to urge families to be collaborated and stay away from any case of separation, quarrel and hatred because of the negative impact on the effort and effectiveness of their students in educational institutions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Al-Dahir ,K.A.(2012). Self concept between theoretical and application. Amman: Dar Wael.
- [2] Al-Dahir ,K.A.(2015). Introduction to special education , Amman :Dar Wael .
- [3] Al-Huli, A. A and Sheldan, F. K. (2012). The causes of educational waste among post graduate students at the Islamic University in Gaza and ways of treatment. The Second Arab International Conference for Quality Assurance of Higher Education.
- [4] Balsa,A., Giuliano.L. and French,M. (2011). The effects of alcohol use on academic achievement in high school . Econ Educ Rev. 2011 , 30(1): 1–15.23
- [5] Cambridge Assessment International Education : Assessment for Learning. <https://www.cambridgeinternational.org/Images/271179-assessment-for-learning.pdf>.
- [6] Dickson,O.(2018).effect of extrinsic motivation on secondary school students academic achievement in social studies . International Journal of Education (IJE), 6(3),1-7.

- [7] Doli,L.(2018).The impact of home environment factors on academic achievement of adolescents . Journal of Arts, Science & Commerce .4(1):137-147.
- [8] Hill, N.E., & Tyson, D.F. (2009). Parental Involvement in Middle School: A MetaAnalytic Assessment of the Strategies That Promote Achievement. *Developmental Psychology*, 45(3), 740-763.
- [9] Makamure,C.(2018). Evoking motivation for achievement in O level mathematics in Zimbabwe. *International Journal of Education (IJE) Vol.6, No.4, 13-21*
- [10] Mkumbo , Kitila,A.K.,& Amani ,Jacueline .(2012). Perceived university student' attribution of their academic success and failure. *Asian Social Science ,Vol.8, No.7*
- [11] Muhasna,A.,Alzubi,Z.,Muhansa,A.,Betaina,U.,and Alzubi,A.(2013). The reasons for the decline in the cumulative average of the students of the Hashemite University from students' point of view *Derasat, Educational Sciences, 40: 1 .*
- [12] Muthoni,K.L.(2013).Relationship between family background and academic performance of secondary schools students: A case of Siakago Divion, Mbeere, North District, Kenya.Master of Art:The University of Nairobi.
- [13] Najimi,A ., Sharifirad,G., Amini,M.M and Meftagh,S.D .(2013). Academic failure and students' viewpoint: The influence of individual, internal and external organizational factors. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion . 2: 22.*
- [14] Raines,T.S., Gordon,M.,Harrel -Williams,L.,Diliborto,R.A.,&Parke,E.M.(2017). Adaptive skills and academic achievement in Latino students .*Journal of Applied School Psychology,33(4)245-260*
- [15] Reda,H&Mulugeta.G.(2018).Investigation the causes of students less academic performance in engineering college of Debre Berhan University .*American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics ,7(3):126-131 .*
- [16] TabassumKhan,N.,&Ahmed,S.(2018). Impact of facebook addiction on student academic performance .*Research in Medical and Engineering Sciences,5,2*
- [17] Talafaha, F. (2006). Reasons for the low cumulative rates of warning students: field diagnostic study on a sample of students of the University of Mu'tah. *University of Damascus Journal ,22:2*
- [18] Trchie,S.A.,& Chiresha,R.(2013). High failure rate in mathematics examinations in rural senior secondary schools in Mthatha District, Eastern Cape:Learners attributions *Stud TribesTribals,11(1):67-73 .*
- [19] Yagan wali,U.G.,Ali,H.K., and Bufarafa,M.W.(2015).Gnder ddifference in student's academic performance in college of education in Borno,Nigeria: Implication for counseling. *Journal of Education and Practice,6(32):107-114.*

AUTHORS

Kahtan Ahmed Al-Dahir is a Professor in special education (college of Art and Sciences ,Department of Special Education and College of Pharmacy and Medical sciences ,Department of Audiology and Speech Pathology) at Al-Ahliyya Amman university .I have many books and articles in the field of special education and educational psychology . I taught many subjects for the stages of bachelor's, master's and doctoral degrees. and supervised and discussed many Masters and PhD students.

